

Experience in the Implementation of FAIR Data Principles in the WGI AR6 Assessment

From challenges to lessons learned and recommendations for future practices (V1 11/08/2022)

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Lessons learned from the AR6 experience and recommendations for AR7 are being developed by the IPCC Working Group I Technical Support Unit (WGI TSU) and Data Distribution Centre (DDC) representatives based on the implementation of FAIR Data Principles in the WGI AR6 Assessment. To facilitate the implementation of FAIR principles, these need to be adopted as a core practice within the assessment process from the start of the AR7. Authors need to be provided with clear instructions on mandatory requirements, templates accompanied by guidance and online tools to assemble information, with a clear timeline. Dedicated TSU staff is needed to support authors and work with the DDC. Dedicated DDC resources are needed to staff this work for the duration of the cycle. Attention to resources for the end of the cycle timeline is needed since a substantial part of the archival and curation work will be completed, including fully interconnecting the code and data products with the report itself. Oversight and guidance is needed throughout the process. The IPCC Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data) has a role as a persistent group here, as well as Working Group Bureau members.

Challenge	AR6 experience	AR7 lessons learned and recommendations
<p>1. Novelty of the implementation of FAIR data principles - new roles, workflows for TSU and DDC.</p>	<p>With the additional complexity of collecting dataset lists, software, provenance information and data citations, a lot of technical pieces have to be developed by the TSU and the DDC Partners.</p> <p>TSU staffing has had to be strengthened during the assessment process to deal with the additional burden of the FAIR Guidelines aspects. Staff time constraints have caused a delay in providing the input dataset lists to the DDC and increasing the effort for the DDC Partner.</p>	<p>Dedicated full-time TSU staff member in support of the DDC Partners is required. At the DDC Partner DKRZ an additional software developer is required in support of the IPCC authors and the TSU and to increase the coverage of CMIP6 input dataset usage and decrease the burden for the DDC.</p> <p>The role of the DDC within the IPCC should be defined as a precondition for a sustainable funding model for the DDC with national and external funders.</p> <p>Handover of the WGI GitHub repository, scripts and best practice/experience around the FAIR Guidelines</p>

	<p>DDC Partners are partially understaffed for the additional tasks related to the FAIR Guidelines causing a further delay in the AR6 long-term data archival. Future funding of the DDC Partners is not sustainable and the status of the DDC within IPCC is undefined.</p> <p>Challenges related to the novelty of curating intermediate datasets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Surprise in volume of intermediate datasets produced by WGI assessment ● Understanding the structure of the original data and mapping it to DKRZ's internal archival structure ● Difficulties with duplicates and missing files and gathering of missing information from the authors ● Assembling information on data usage within the AR6 (chapter, figure) ● Checking that the datasets comply with input data license restrictions <p>Challenges related to the novelty to select CMIP6 input datasets based on IPCC author information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incompleteness of CMIP6 input dataset usage ● Insufficient review of CMIP6 list content requiring additional review steps at DKRZ ● Difficulties to interpret the given figure usage information ● Difficulties deriving CMIP6 citations from author information for Data References in the AR6 (Annex II) required DKRZ staff to support the TSU. 	<p>implementation to the AR7 is required.</p>
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<p>2. Challenges faced by authors of contributing to a process put in place during the assessment.</p>	<p>Author's involvement and responsiveness:</p>			<p>The author tasks should be a standard requirement for each author as part of the process to prepare report figures.</p> <p>Including a data scientist role in every chapter has been discussed but this approach would not fit the practices with how IPCC author teams are built. Selecting authors with experience and interest in FAIR data principles and good practices in open source code development and data sharing would be very helpful (e.g. use of systematic and standardised methods to create resources associated with data). The terms of reference of chapter scientists could be extended to include data and code aspects to support CLAs and authors in ensuring the tasks are completed by the chapters.</p> <p>We recommend the figure of a communication bridge between scientists and repositories. This is essential to work fluently and help to understand the constraints which both extremes of the chain deal with. (desired skills: experience as a researcher, background in climate changes and awareness of relevance of the provided resources, experience in data management, data curation and application of FAIR practices)</p> <p>Further development of author support tools is needed.</p>
	<p>TSU call for data and code</p>	<p>Corrections and updates (emails, reminders, new corrections)</p>	<p>Catalogue record preparation (final check)</p>	
<p>High interest and involvement</p> <p></p>				
<p>Since this has been a first-time effort, data and software have been collected from the authors a soft approach has been taken to deadlines, e.g. no hard deadline to assemble code and data after the FDG. This causes delays and is communication-intensive for the TSU to follow up with authors.</p> <p>Data and software providers in the chapters did not exist as a role in the chapters. The TSU has mainly coordinated this work with chapter scientists. This has gone beyond the terms of reference of this role in the AR6. Many chapter scientists, but not all, have code and data skills, the interface generally works since chapter scientists often work on chapter figures, however this was intended as an interface to the author team, not an expectation that chapter scientists do all the tasks.</p>				

	<p>However, the burden was significantly carried by the chapter scientists, which placed a considerable workload on them with delays when working on the main chapter scientist tasks.</p>	
<p>3. Missing datasets, code and metadata.</p>	<p>For various chapters the code, input data, and licence was not available which has made challenging the follow up with the authors in order to collect all the missing information. For example, missing metadata is usually the temporal/geographic extent and/or keywords/authors.</p> <p>The relevance of metadata completeness, i.e. providing key additional information to the archived data, may seem to authors as a waste of time at the beginning of the process. However, when the data starts to be used it saves considerable time to the data providers, speeds up the use of the data and allows for accurate tracking errors.</p>	<p>Make the data and software requirements an integral part of the AR7 timeline and include them into chapter deliveries for FOD, SOD and FDG.</p> <p>Provide to the authors since the beginning of the assessment, guidelines on how to organise the code and the input data in the IPCC WGI Github repository by following the FAIR guidelines and/or an agreed standard.</p> <p>Support from the beginning: One way to make the most of the collaborative action between authors and data curators is to provide clear objectives and rules from the beginning. Keep it simple and clear without missing the requirement of crucial information for the potential users. The use of simple templates has been very helpful for this process.</p>
<p>4. Quality control process.</p>	<p>The process is laborious and time consuming if performed by the single authors, TSU or DDC staff and can hold up the timeline to publishing the code and datasets. Quality check (during the process we have found inconsistencies between data and plots, this has helped to improve the results: 3 of 10 SPM figures, 1 TS</p>	<p>Quality check: This process is very recommended, in particular for the final data. These resources might be used by non-expert users, therefore assuring that the data reproduce the final plot without any errors is fundamental to protect the quality of the results coming from the use of the data.</p>

	<p>figure, several report figures). Time consuming but helpful to improve the final product (not only the data but the report itself).</p>	<p>Input datasets should become an integral part of the quality checks / review process. Software needs to be developed and put in place to support this.</p> <p>Furthermore consistency checks of CMIP6 input data archive and documentations in final data archive and supplementary material of the report should be introduced.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal review by TSU (at least for the figures that will be used massively i.e. SPM, TS, FAQ and CCBOX in the report) ● Collaboration of volunteer authors ● Peer review by programming communities (ESMValTool)
<p>5. Ensuring that licensing constraints are met.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extra checks are needed for datasets embedded in code and Jupyter scripts to be able to distribute this data via the WGI GitHub or DDC. ● Intermediate data licensing - IPCC products should follow DDC license policy - needs input data licensing to be compatible or waivers need to be agreed before distribution of intermediate datasets with CC-BY-4.0 licence. ● Licensing constraints in final data have only been encountered for one figure (ch2_ccb1_fig1). Suggestions for how to proceed are being discussed with TSU and CEDA. 	<p>Require metadata on any licensing constraints associated with datasets and code at the start of the documentation process.</p>

<p>6. Challenges for established curation practices.</p>	<p>Related to data format, quality control issues, incomplete/errors in documentation, curation of Jupyter notebook structure, etc.</p> <p>Is not so straightforward to find a balance between the practices of authors and the requirements and restrictions for long term archival, as well as supporting user needs and the proper use of code and datasets. The adaptation and synchronisation between these elements have been very time consuming and require adopting flexible approaches to find practical solutions and move forwards with making code and datasets available.</p> <p>Different repository structures – Chapter 7 and 9 have been organised into pre-existing GitHub repos by the chapter authors/contributors - for Ch9 we decided to grab the datasets directly from GitHub (bypassing arrivals stage) and create catalogue records manually (using metadata from figure captions and Figure Manager). Process for Chapter 7 is ongoing. Long-term preservation is a question we will need to address – linking time-tagged GitHub releases to a DOI on Zenodo and adding this to record documentation was an internal CEDA suggestion.</p> <p>File naming conventions for CEDA archive – avoiding confusion means ambiguous characters/those common in Unix commands are not allowed – in this case we rename the file to match our standards, modifying also</p>	
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	<p>the readme.txt, metadata.yaml and info in the catalogue record, and add a clarification in the record.</p> <p>In case of the CMIP6 input dataset archival at DKRZ, the challenges lie in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the late provision due to TSU staff constraints and the lower priority, ● the amount of information to be provided by the the authors, ● the complexity of the process to collect and merge the information from the authors. <p>This required DKRZ to add two additional steps to the new interface developed for CMIP6 dataset archival:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● check and correct or complete provided information before merging, and ● compensate incompleteness by adding an additional archival workflow to curate the datasets specified by the authors at the start of AR6. <p>Due to the delay, some CMIP6 input datasets are no longer available in the ESGF and cannot be archived.</p>	
<p>7. Interconnecting archived and curated data and code to the report.</p>	<p>User/reader navigation among WGI AR6 products (printed and web-based report) needs to be developed and put in place. Direct links to relevant GitHub repositories and data catalogue entries are planned. These will be provided alongside the figures on the report website.</p>	<p>Develop automatic ways of connecting information and links to code and datasets as entries alongside figure files as the report website is put in place, and to communicate any updates and changes.</p>

	<p>How to integrate information on intermediate datasets into the online digital report is under consideration; an integration of CMIP6 input datasets may be too challenging at this stage.</p>	
<p>8. Implementation of IPCC Error Protocol for data and code.</p>	<p>Integration of intermediate and input data into the IPCC Error Protocol is needed that involves actions and documentation by the DDC as part of the process when needed. A workflow for error handling is being prepared by WGI TSU with the DDC.</p> <p>Information on data usage of the CMIP6 datasets in the AR6 has still to be made usable; information for intermediate data to be added to the metadata</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● required for efficient errata treatment reported to IPCC with trickle backs to input/intermediate data; ● required to report input data errors reported through CMIP6 and the DDC to the IPCC. 	<p>Implementation of a workflow for error handling that includes an iteration with the DDC if errors in datasets or code are identified.</p>
<p>9. Time pressure towards the end of assessment.</p>	<p>Delays and limited resources increase time pressure on implementing the work due to termination of the TSU existence at the end of the assessment cycle and reductions in or end of DDC funding. Yet efforts have been required for additional workflow tasks or new workflows altogether.</p> <p>Data archival will take longer than the TSU period.</p>	<p>Define the interim period between assessment cycles and the handover process. An improved workflow, hands-on assistance and provision and application of software tools to support authors and the review process can help to decrease the time pressure.</p>

	Therefore, the contact for establishing and maintaining cross-links between AR6 (chapters) is unclear.	
<p>10. Awareness building and guidance on what resources are available and for their proper use.</p>	<p>Data is used more intensively when there are events or announcements related to climate change. For example: Figure SPM.2 https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/c1eb6dad1598427f8f9f3eae346ece2f has been used more than 2000 times without the need of any additional support by the TSU or DDC.</p> <p>Proper use of the data: (example Interactive Atlas case (Tom Février, Les Echos): data that has been used country by country instead of using them in the predefined regions for which they have been created.</p>	Engaging ways to train potential users are needed, also to identify features of potential users to successfully promote the use of the data.